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The role of ICT as LT in shaping inclusive and special education – a systematic review for 2012–2023

Abstract:

Purpose: Digital inequalities are pressing concerns, especially for students in need of special educational support. In recent years, numerous reviews have been published on the use of learning technologies (LT) in inclusive and special education. They mostly provide findings for specific groups, technologies, and countries. This systematic review aims to identify changes in the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) as LT that evolved globally in inclusive and special education over the last 12 years.

Methodology: Web of Science, Scopus, and EBSCOhost were systematically searched for publications for 2012 to 2023. Only peer-reviewed English publications were included to ensure a comprehensive review. The findings of the 421 included papers were then analysed, reflecting diverse perspectives at the technology, learners, teachers, and institutional levels.

Findings: The most used devices were computers, iPads/tablets, and specifically designed apps. More studies were conducted in separate settings than in inclusive ones. The primary participant groups were students on the autism spectrum. More than half the research publications were related to technology use. Technology development was the most common research objective, with approximately 40% of test hypotheses based on standardised tests or observations.

Implications: By shifting the focus from specific disabilities to a more usability-based approach, we can envision a future in which the quality of education for all students is substantially improved.

Originality: All data were meticulously collected and analysed to ensure credibility and originality.

Keywords - Systematic Review, Information and Communication Technologies, Learning Technology, Inclusive and Special Education.

Article classification: Peer-Reviewed Paper, Literature review

1. Introduction

In societies where Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) are crucial, unequal access to them is linked to disparities in social participation (van Dijk, 2005). Digital inequality is often discussed in the discourse on digitalisation. The discourse on digital inequality among people with disabilities (Dobransky and Hargittai, 2016) often goes along with discussions on the digital divide (Ragnedda and Ruiu, 2018) and digital inclusion (Hartnett, 2022). The tension between digital inequality and digital inclusion can be explained by the paradox of technology, which involves the simultaneous ability to provide opportunities and limit access and inclusion (Roulstone, 2016, p. 3). In recent years, the living situations of people with disabilities have received increasing attention in these discussions (Goggin, 2021, p. 255), as evidenced by terms such as ‘disability divide’ (Dobransky and Hargittai, 2016) and ‘digital disability divide’ (Sachdeva *et al.*, 2015). Technology can be disabling rather than enabling, particularly for people with disabilities (Goggin, 2021, p. 256).

ICT, when used as learning Technology (LT), can contribute to ‘ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all’ (UNESCO, 2017, p. 18). In the digitalised world, participation in education also depends on the opportunities that students have to use LT (OECD, 2023). However, the wide range of abilities and needs of students in need of special educational support make providing adequate LT (assistive technology as well as generic technology) challenging. LT can expand the possibilities of teaching, learning, and access to information (OECD, 2023, p. 9).

This starting point has led us to ask what we know about LT for students in need of special educational support. Based on a literature review by Nussbaumer and Hövel (2021), the review presented here provides an overview for researchers and school professionals planning studies or using LT. Nussbaumer and Hövel’s review has some limitations. The breadth of the search terms was restricted, affecting both the ICT and special needs domains. These limitations resulted in few relevant hits and failed to encompass the full scope of ICT use in inclusive and special education. The current study aims to rectify these limitations using a broad search string to capture a more comprehensive view.

1.1 Need for special educational support

Recognising that inclusive education is defined differently in different national contexts (Messiou and Ainscow, 2020), we outline our understanding. The ‘Education for all and especially for some’ (Lütje-Klose, 2023, p. 18) approach refers to all students, especially vulnerable groups and responds with special measures and compensation for disadvantages. These differences can emerge in schools as special educational needs (SEN) (Lütje-Klose, 2023, p. 17). An internationally broadly accepted definition of SEN originates from the Department for Education and Department for Health (2015):

A child or young person has SEN if they have a learning difficulty or disability, which calls for special educational support to be made for him or her. A child of compulsory school age or a young person has a learning difficulty or disability if he or she:

- has a significantly more incredible difficulty in learning than most others of the same age, or
- has a disability which prevents or hinders him or her from using facilities of a kind generally provided for others of the same age in mainstream schools or mainstream post-16 institutions. (pp. 15-16)

According to the WHO’s bio-psycho-social concept of disability, a disability is not linked to people but to participation in life situations (World Health Organization, 2001). Successful participation in

learning situations depends crucially on environmental factors. An important environmental factor is the technology used. We use the term 'students in need of special educational support', as proposed by Lidström *et al.* (2020), to stress the role LT can fulfil as an environmental enabling or disabling factor. This special educational support, which can also, but not only be provided by LT, must be considered at the level of the learners, the teachers and the institutions.

1.2 Learning Technology

Dealing with ICT has the same issues for all students: its use as an educational tool (e.g. for knowledge gathering) and the promotion of media literacy (e.g. understanding of how the media works, being able to evaluate what you see; Buckingham, 2005). For students in need of special educational support, ICT can serve as an alternative tool for learning (e.g. for processing-adapted learning tasks) and as a compensatory tool (e.g. typing with a Braille keyboard) (Lidström *et al.*, 2011). Using ICT for assessment and management in special education is also essential; however, our study focused on the use of learning technology (LT) in classrooms.

In special needs education, the term assistive technology has become established, which is closely aligned with the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (World Health Organization, 2001). The Individuals with Disabilities Education Act - IDEA 2004, Part A, Sec. 602.), defines:

"The term 'assistive technology' means any item, device, or product system, whether commercially available or modified or customised, that is designed to augment, maintain, or improve the functional abilities of a child with a disability."

As the term 'assistive technology' is primarily used in special education and also includes non-technical aids, we prefer the term LT. Another reason is that we are interested in the use of technologies in special and inclusive education. The term LT includes both assistive technologies and general ICT used in special and inclusive education. We consider all types of uses of ICT in education as LT (Liu *et al.*, 2013; Lidström *et al.*, 2011).

Whether ICT as a LT enables someone's learning depends on who uses it, at which educational level, and for what reason. This review aims to identify changes in the use of LT in inclusive and special education and to locate existing gaps in research. To achieve this, we first examined the available reviews to identify gaps and determine areas requiring further systematic review.

2. Literature review: findings and inspiration from previous studies

Using the same methodology as for the literature review in total (Page *et al.*, 2021), we identified 40 reviews, three meta-analyses and one combined review/ meta-analyses on the use of ICT as a LT in special and inclusive education published between 2012 and 2023. Most reviews focused on specific technologies or target groups, e.g. the use of augmented reality for students with ASD (Denizli-Gulboy *et al.*, 2023) or even on specific scientific journals like a review for 25 years of the Journal of Special Educational Technology (Sinha *et al.*, 2024). Among these systematic reviews was the one by Liu *et al.* (2013). The authors conducted an analysis (N=26) from 2008 to 2012 that examined the trends of LT implementation in special education. Their review identified that the primary focus of these studies was to evaluate the learning effectiveness of LT, with experimental designs being the most common methodological approach. Computer-assisted technologies have been frequently employed, particularly for students with intellectual disabilities. The review for 1970 to 2011 by Starcic and Bagon (2014) was also a pivotal reference point (N=118). Almost half of the papers were published after 2006, the most frequent group were children with specific learning difficulties. The

authors called for research on the pedagogical use of ICTs to be significantly intensified and for all students to be addressed equally (Starcic and Bagon, 2014).

The report of the European Agency for Special and Inclusive Education on inclusive digital education was grounded in a review of the years 2016 to 2021. The literature review revealed only a small overlap between the literature on inclusive and digital education (Weber *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, the medical model of disability still greatly influences research. This report showed that many studies focus on using technologies for precisely differentiated target groups. The concept of a universal learning design has rarely been addressed. Some technologies may have high potential for inclusive education, but the content is insufficient for use (Weber *et al.*, 2022). Although the results of this report are influential at the political level in Europe, this publication did mainly not follow the procedure for scientific systematic reviews.

Large differences in the number of hits become clear when searching exclusively in established databases such as ERIC or Web of Science. On this methodological basis, Fernández-Batanero *et al.* identified 31 studies between 2009-2020 on the use of AT for inclusive education. "Findings of this study include that the use of AT is successful in increasing the inclusion and accessibility of students with disabilities, although barriers such as teacher education, lack of information or accessibility are found. (2022, p. 1011).

In addition to these literature reviews, other reviews have been presented for specific countries. For example, Edyburn published a rapid literature review about the use of assistive technology in education in Australia, Canada, the United Kingdom, and the United States from 2005 to 2019 in 2020. The findings reveal a knowledge base of 950 documents with 96 reviews. "This rapid review provides evidence regarding AT applications for all special needs and disabilities at all levels of the educational system" (Edyburn, 2020, p.6).

Most of the reviews available to date relate to individual groups of people, address individual technologies, or are related to selected countries or journals. Some of the reports and reviews found do not fulfill the requirements of systematic scientific reviews or only use a few selected databases. The reviews contain only a few large-scale studies. Numerous studies use qualitative methods with a small number of participants. Overall, existing reviews show that the tangible impact of the use of LT in inclusive and special education is difficult to assess, first, because of the speed of technological development, second, because of the very personalised use of ICTs by students in need of special educational support; and third, because of the strongly divergent international school systems and the associated differences in terminology.

Our review aims to provide a systematic international overview of LT used in inclusive and special education and in which settings. Due to our understanding of disability caused by environmental factors, we are especially interested in whether the focus is more on learning situations for the entire class or on separate groups or individuals. Central to this systematic review are the following research questions:

1. What are the primary research aims, methodologies, and outcomes of recent studies on ICT as a LT in special and inclusive education?
2. What types of ICT as a LT are predominantly used and for which kinds of students in need of special educational support?

It seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse on digital inequality and inclusion by locating research gaps and demonstrating how LT can improve education quality. The types of educational technology used are subject to constant change. New trends can be observed every year, and profound evolution can be expected at intervals of three to four years (Guaña-Moya *et al.*, 2022). The review

presented here covers the past 12 years to capture the substantial technological advancements that have occurred in this timeframe. This period has witnessed remarkable progress in various fields, including computing power, artificial intelligence, and communication technologies, impacting research and applications across multiple disciplines.

3. Method

The methodological approach is based on the guidelines for a systematic literature review formulated in the PRISMA statement (Page et al., 2021).

3.1 Search strategy

The search was limited to English-language publications with peer review. We focused on the primary and secondary school levels in the context of inclusive and special education.

In January 2024, the ERIC, APA PsychINFO, PSYINDEX Education Research Complete, and Education Source databases were accessed via EBSCOhost, and in February 2024, Web of Science and Scopus were accessed. The search parameters used were as follows:

A) Publication year 2012–2023

B) English language

C) Age groups: child (0–18 years), childhood (birth–12 years), adolescence (13–17 years), child (6–12 years), school age (6–12 years), and adolescence (13–18 years).

There were some overlapping and similar-age exclusions due to the incorporation of different primary databases into the search. The search focused on abstracts.

3.2 Inclusion process

To incorporate the terms broadly, five volumes of three significant journals were examined for LT terminology by searching the titles and abstracts of individual articles (*Journal of Enabling Technologies, Technology and Disability, and Educational Technology & Society*). The search terms were used as strings with Boolean operators. The search terms were divided into three categories: The first category represented the characterisation of ICT. Next to general search terms such as Information and Communication Technolog* or ICT or assistive technology*, we used terms for specific devices such as iPad or tablets and search strings for specific technological developments such as artificial intelligence or big data. The second category referred to the school context. The last category is referred to as special educational needs. Next to general search terms such as SEN or Special Education, we used terms concerning specific groups of students, like low vision or autism spectrum disorder and for specific impairments like cerebral palsy or Down syndrome.

Figure 1. Exclusion and inclusion process: PRISMA flow chart (Page et al., 2020)

figure by authors

The search yielded 5067 hits. **See figure 1.** A rigorous process has been done to eliminate duplicate records. Initially, duplicate entries were identified and removed using the reference management software Citavi. Citavi's built-in duplicate detection feature was employed, which compares entries based on various criteria such as title, author names, and publication year, allowing for an efficient first pass in duplicate elimination. Following this automated process, we exported the remaining references to an Excel spreadsheet for further manual verification. In Excel, we sorted the entries by author and title to facilitate the identification of any remaining duplicates. This manual review was conducted by our research team, who carefully screened each entry to ensure that all duplicates were removed.

After eliminating duplicates, non-English publications, and publications with the wrong age, the abstracts of the remaining 3455 hits were manually checked for a) particular educational references, b) school references (including checking for the desired school levels), and c) ICT references by the project team with the support of three junior researchers. Our research team extracted data from the papers in the final corpus. Each full text was carefully read, and notes were taken on specific categories deemed critical for our analysis. These categories included age, the disability group addressed in the study, the setting or environment in which the study was conducted (e.g., inclusive, separative), the primary research question or objective of the study, and the main findings and outcomes reported. The research team used standard data extraction forms to facilitate this process to ensure consistency and comprehensiveness. By manually reviewing and annotating each paper, we ensured a thorough and detailed extraction of data, which is crucial for the subsequent synthesis. This resulted in 627 studies. Based on the 619 retrieved full texts, studies were excluded if they were deemed irrelevant to the research question by consensus within the authors' team after a second review. Finally, 421 peer-reviewed studies remained.

Tables 1-3. Studies on the use of ICT as LT in inclusive and special education **(JET Website)**

The results were systematically categorised based on the Ecosystem of Inclusive Education Model of the European Agency for Special and Inclusive Education, based on Bronfenbrenner and Ceci’s (1994) model. The model guided differentiation between the 1. technology level, 2. learner’s level, 3. teachers’ level, and 4. institutional level (Weber *et al.*, 2022). The analysis was based on these dimensions and focused on the contributions and risks of LT for access and equitable participation in education, including the possibilities of using LT to enable, support, or improve inclusive teaching and learning.

4. Data extraction and synthesis of results

The following characteristics were systematically collected for the descriptive synthesis of all the studies: research question(s), research aim, research methods and instruments, sample size, school level, age, type of impairment(s), type of ICT, educational setting, country, and origin.

4.1 Descriptive data

Between 2012 and 2023, an average of 35 studies were published each year, with a peak of 48 publications in 2020 and 41 studies during the pandemic in 2021. The studies originated from 38 countries, with a majority (183) from the US and 45 from the UK. Most studies focused on special education (139), followed by general education (77), psychology (54), and health sciences (45).

Regarding methodology, 171 studies tested hypotheses, with 50 using a randomised controlled trial, 48 using a quasi-experimental design, and 73 using a single-case research design. These associations were examined statistically in 123 studies. Of the studies, 74 employed qualitative methods for theory building, while seven used a mixed-methods design, and the design could not be identified in 28. Most studies used standardised tests or observations as data collection methods.

The sample size ranged from a minimum of one participant to a maximum of 20,863 participants. The mean sample size was 109 children and adolescents. However, the median was nine students when all sample sizes were arranged in ascending order. This suggests that, while the mean sample size was relatively high, most studies had small to medium sample sizes, and only a few had exceptionally high numbers of participants.

The age of the study participants ranged from 2 to 74 years, including studies covering a more comprehensive age range than school age. The mean age was 12 years, and the median was 11 years. Regarding the forms of disabilities and disorders addressed, most studies (165) investigated the use of ICT for and with students with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). This was followed by 103 studies on learning disorders and 73 studies on hearing impairments. As the studies also included participants with multiple disabilities, the overall number exceeded the number of studies. The different disabilities are considered approximately equal in the four-year blocks. An exception is ASD. In 2012–2015 and 2016–2019, ASD was addressed in 60 studies. In contrast, in 2020–2023, it was addressed in only 40 studies.

Table 4. Types of ICT, as LT mentioned in the papers

Type of ICT	Total
Computer	124
iPad	63
App	43
serious game	34
assistive technology	31
Video	25
Tablet	24
Internet	18
virtual reality	14

n.d.	14
robots	12
AAC	11
smartphone	11
distance learning	10
augmented reality	5
e-learning	5
social media	4
3D printing	1

Table 4 shows all the ICTs used and examined. With 124 instances, studies most often referred to the term ‘computer’. The ‘iPad’ was the second most frequently investigated item (63 times) in special education, followed by specific apps in 43 studies. No overall trend was observed in the use of different ICT categories in the comparison of four years each. An exception was the ICT category ‘Computer’. The number of studies decreased from 52 in 2012–2015 to 41 in 2016–2019 and 29 in 2020–2023.

Regarding the setting where the studies were conducted, the separate forms of schooling were explicitly stated more frequently (167) than an explicit notion of the inclusive form of schooling (127). The studies' frequencies in the two separation and inclusion settings were evenly distributed over the years.

4.2 Category-based synthesis of results

4.2.1 Technology level: Technology's potential to advance inclusion

A total of 252 studies focused on technology's potential to advance inclusion, accounting for 60% of the 421 included studies. Most studies were conducted in primary schools, 70 in secondary schools, and 12 covered school-age students in general. The participants included individuals with ASD and intellectual disabilities, and most studies were conducted in separative settings. The most common country of origin for these studies was the US, followed by the UK.

Most studies focused on evaluating technology, primarily computers in general (76), serious games (25), and iPads/tablets (12). The research questions were widespread: some validated or improved the design of the technology used, some compared different ICTs, some tested the effectiveness of interventions and methods, and some investigated improvement in learning outcomes using ICTs (communication, language, mathematics) or the situation at schools concerning the awareness and utilisation of AT.

An examination of studies related to ICT for students with neurodevelopmental disorders revealed that web-based interventions can be effective. These studies mainly used technology such as computers, iPads, and tablets to improve learning outcomes in reading, writing, and arithmetic. Multimodal approaches that engage multiple senses had more significant learning effects (e.g. Porter, 2022;). Numerous studies focused on serious games. Users showed increased motivation and engagement when integrating digital games into inclusive education (e.g. Yildirim and Surer, 2021).

Twenty-three studies also delved into the subcategory of the use of AT by students, mainly those with ASD and physical disabilities. Positive outcomes were reported in engagement, communication skills, and classroom performance. The importance of involving individuals with disabilities in the development of technological applications was highlighted. Teachers benefitted from co-learning, as they helped learners with special needs acquire assistive technology skills (e.g. Wiley *et al.*, 2016). Overall, the studies demonstrated various positive effects of AT in educational settings, such as improved computer usage, enhanced classroom performance, increased communication skills, and

reduced accessibility barriers. However, the studies also highlighted the need for individualised approaches and ongoing support to ensure the successful integration and use of AT in educational tasks.

Only eight studies addressed the subcategory universal design for learning (UDL). Studies that dealt with UDL were found; however, owing to the lack of ICT references, these were not included in the final selection.

4.2.2 Learner's Level: Learners and inclusion in digital education

Forty-one studies were included in this category. Only 12 were attributable to inclusive education and 17 to separative education. The first subcategory, 'learning environments and settings', comprised 27 studies. Some studies investigated the impact of different presentation media and teaching methods on children's cognitive and learning abilities, focusing mainly on students on the autistic spectrum. However, interactivity did not influence learning, and labelling did not improve symbolic understanding (e.g. Wainwright, 2020). In distance learning learners with sensorineural impairments faced challenges due to communication barriers and dissatisfaction with access to services (e.g. Bubbico *et al.*, 2021). Mixed results emerged regarding blended learning for students experiencing learning difficulties.

4.2.3 Teachers' level: Teachers and digital education

Of the 421 studies, 101 focused on teachers and digital education. Most studies fell into the subcategory of 'inclusive media didactics', which covered didactical questions. The samples in these 74 studies were almost evenly distributed between primary and secondary schools. Among the three types of learning disabilities, 29 studies focused on learning disabilities, 24 on autism, and 13 on intellectual disabilities. Other types of disabilities were represented in eight studies. Many studies were conducted in both inclusive (30) and separative (29) settings. The studies often focused on interventions related to specific subjects (especially languages, mathematics, and STEM education) or individual and general academic skills, such as handwriting. These studies emphasised the potential of individualised and evidence-based approaches using technology. For instance, math interventions highlighted the effectiveness of apps, video self-modelling, and iPad apps in promoting math proficiency and engagement. Furthermore, various studies explored handwriting differences using ICT assessments, and longitudinal studies focused on improving handwriting accuracy for different diagnoses, such as learning disabilities and motor difficulties. These studies showed that technology can enhance learning outcomes, engagement, and skills across different domains. They also emphasised the importance of tailored approaches and teacher collaboration for students with diverse learning needs. Successful technology integration in classrooms simultaneously requires both a clear technology vision and pedagogical expertise.

Moreover, of the 421 studies identified, only 4 could be assigned to the institutional level.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In the discussion, we first turn to the research question: What types of ICT as a LT are predominantly used and for which kinds of students in need of special educational support?

This review highlights that most studies focus on students within the autistic spectrum. Statistical differences can be identified in the three intervals. The decreasing number of studies on this target group in the last interval (2019–2023) could indicate that the dominance of this group decreasing. A key question arises: Does the use of LT relate to individuals or to the whole class, positioning LT as an environmental factor? The overwhelming number of studies have focused on the technology level.

The most established technologies are computers, followed by tablets, especially iPads. This raises the question of whether currently dominant technological trends, such as artificial intelligence, have so far attracted little research interest in the context of inclusive education and for which reasons.

Concerning the research questions on primary research aims, methodologies, and outcomes, the results show existing research gaps, particularly in long-term studies, and the role of educational institutions. It would be beneficial to conduct large-scale studies to gather representative data, especially for students with rare impairments, for which little comparative data is available to date. The absence of data for students with special educational needs in regular large-scale studies on the use of learning technologies (LT) in schools and media-related skills could be due to the selection of survey instruments that are not accessible for all students in need of special educational support (Bosse & Haage, 2020) or because the study organizers do not collect or report data on this topic due to different understandings of inclusive education. Having comparisons on the use and effectiveness of educational technologies and the acquisition of digitalization-related skills for all students is crucial for education policy to make informed decisions on funding LT and the training of teachers and other education professionals.

Research intensity has increased. Tables 1-3 allow researchers and practitioners to see for which groups of people and educational technologies, as well as for which educational contexts, research has taken place over the last twelve years. Next to significant results how LT can improve the quality of inclusive education, the systematic review identified several gaps. Furthermore, the majority of the studies were carried out in the discipline of special education. This raises the question of which understanding of inclusion the study was based on in each case. In many cases, it was not possible to find data about this. Often, no information was available on whether the study occurred in an inclusive setting. A rarely addressed topic is digital inequalities, which investigates where (new) barriers and inequalities are (re)produced and how media can enable participation within digital spaces. In line with the European Agency for Special and Inclusive Education report, we can also confirm that there has been little overlap 'between literature on inclusive education and literature on digital education' (Weber *et al.*, 2022, p. 38). The medical model identified in the European Agency report was also influential in our review, focusing on learners from a deficit-orientated perspective.

We identified a considerable number of studies about didactical issues. Most studies focused on language, mathematics, and communication interventions. Although UDL is intensively discussed, it was hardly present in the analysed studies, and its implications were often not widely acknowledged. Research on media didactics was available only for separative settings and students with ASD. There are apparent research gaps in inclusive media didactics and reflexive-critical media education. LT have the potential to significantly contribute to creating the least restrictive learning environment for students in need of special educational support. One step for practitioners is to consider the interdependencies between the different dimensions of heterogeneity relevant to digital inclusion. In order to solve these complex pedagogical tasks appropriately, multidisciplinary cooperation is necessary, involving experts in technical, pedagogical, didactic and inclusive education in digitalised societies.

A systematic literature review is a suitable method for covering a field of research that encompasses several disciplines and includes a variety of research approaches. However, this method has some limitations. Some studies may not have been captured in the search without a well-defined domain or clear and well-defined search terms. Many search terms were used to minimise this possibility and were differentiated several times. When searching via Web of Science, Scopus, and EBSCOhost, the results also depend on the type of records in which the respective university library deposits are

related to the databases to be funded. We failed to use the term “special education technology”, which is quite commonly used, especially in the US, to describe not individual technology like assistive technology but more generic technology used in a special education setting.

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